

IPBES VA Chapter 6 - Brightspot Cases text analysis

Code: IPBES_VA_6.3

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Description: The IPBES VA mandate for Chapter 6 mentions the importance of describing the kinds of capacity-building needed for the explicit acknowledgment of the different types of conceptualization of nature and its benefits and their explicit incorporation into decisions and policy-making at different levels and in different contexts. This coding follows on the VA_4.4_Chapter 4 related to brightspot cases that indeed include a description of how policy instruments could facilitate transformative governance, these bright spot cases are further analyzed as described in this report.

Process overview:

Protocol:

Type of analysis/search/review: Text analysis from the Brightspots cases found in VA_4.4_Ch4

Search languages: English

Exact Coding Date: 5-9 October, 2020

Sample extracted: 70 (A)

Fields extracted (A):

- ID of the study,
- Title of study,
- Authors (comma separated, no superscripts),
- Was a policy instrument mentioned in this case?,

Location and Format of the Data (A): IPBES_VA_6.3_11-12-2020_(A).csv

Treatment applied: First coding applied responds to the application of (R1) to (A)

A + R1 = B

Fields extracted (B):

- ID of the study,
- Title of study,
- Authors (comma separated, no superscripts),
- Was a policy instrument mentioned in this case?,
- Any evidence for diverse value approaches?,
- Elements of transformative governance evident,
- Include,
- Notes,

Sample extracted: 68 (B)

Location and Format of the Data (B): IPBES_VA_6.3_08-04-2020_(B).csv

Treatment applied: Second criteria coding applied responds to the application of **(R2)** to **(B)**

B + R2 = C

Fields extracted (C):

- ID of the study,
- Title of study,
- Authors (comma separated, no superscripts),
- Was a policy instrument mentioned in this case?,
- Any evidence for diverse value approaches?,
- Elements of transformative governance evident,
- Include,
- Notes,
- Person coding
- What policy instruments are associated with the case,
- Category of Policy instrument (Legal and regulatory, Economic and financial, Rights-based and customary norms, Social and cultural),
- Elements of transformative governance presence (Address Status Quo, Address Diverse Values, Stimulate Institutional Changes, Capacity Building, Integrative-Adaptive),
- Decision making contexts (Political decisions & Public actors, Political decisions & private actors, Political decisions & civil society actors, Economic decisions & Public actors, Economic decision & private actors, Economic decisions & civil society actors, Socio-environmental decisions & Public actors, Socio-environmental decisions & private actors, Socio-environmental decisions & civil society actors),
- Stakeholders (Actors and influencers),
- Values,
- Life value frames,
- Scales (Local / Landscape, Provincial / State, National, Regional , International, Cross-scale),
- In which way did the application of policy instruments facilitate (a) incorporation of diverse value approaches, b) transformative change?,
- Leverage Points (Recognition of values, Valuation Methods, Decision-making and Governance, Drivers of change and transformation, Evaluation of outcomes,

Sample extracted: 62 (C)

Location and Format of the Data (C): IPBES_VA_6.3_08-04-2020_(C).xls

Definition of files

ID	Name	Description of file	File Type
A	IPBES_VA_6.3_11-12-2020_(A).csv	Sample extracted	csv
B	IPBES_VA_6.3_08-04-2020_(B).csv	Database after (R1) is applied	csv
C	IPBES_VA_6.3_08-04-2020_(C).csv	Contains the results after R1 and R2 were applied	csv
R1	IPBES_VA_6.2_11-12-2020_(R1).pdf	Applied rules of review (R1)	pdf
R2	IPBES_VA_6.2_11-12-2020_(R2).pdf	Criteria applied to (B)	pdf